

Low-cost sensor node for air quality monitoring: verification of NO₂ measurements against a commercial system

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Abstract

In the light of the current respiratory disease pandemic, air quality gains relevance in cities around the world. Continuously monitoring trends of pollutants with a higher spatial and time resolution is desired to support the information from high quality stations. Given the availability of low-cost sensors and data transmission via wireless networks, it is possible to envision such monitoring with high quality at large scales. Facilitating that smart cities actively influence the distribution of pollutants, for instance, by active traffic control. Thus, offering citizens a better environment to live in. Our sensor-box prototype aims at monitoring air quality and other environmental parameters with lower cost sensors and components. Several challenges exist to achieve sensible measurements from metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) or from electro-chemical (EC) sensors such as: reproducibility, stability, uncertainty, drift, cross sensitivities. Here, the focus is on comparing nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) measurements from these two families of low-cost sensors. Thus, we report on a side-by-side evaluation of the MOS sensor from a commercial system, and the EC sensor in our sensor-box. Recalibration of our EC sensors is demonstrated with a linear fit to the commercial system.

Keywords

Air quality; environmental sensing; nitrogen dioxide; metal oxide semiconductor sensors; electrochemical gas sensors; Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN), Long Range WAN (LoRaWAN)

1. Introduction

Air pollution is one of the main root causes for multiple human illnesses and deaths, thus the associated costs are significant (Künzli, 2010). Since the 1980's, thanks to national environmental policies, air quality in Switzerland has improved. However, recently, ambient concentrations of pollutants such as ozone and nitrogen oxides have exceeded expected levels (European Environment Agency, 2020). Thus, continuous monitoring of the trends of pollutants with a higher space and time resolution is desired to support the information from high quality stations. Given the availability of low-cost sensors and data transmission via wireless networks, it is possible to envision such monitoring with high quality at large scales. Facilitating that smart cities actively influence the distribution of pollutants for instance by traffic control or settlement policy.

Morawska (2019), Karagulian (2019), and Penza (2020) describe research and development efforts on low-cost air quality monitoring, including type sensor technology, platform used to deploy the sensors, and scope of the study or application. Classification of technologies, information on costs and manufactures can also be found in Alexandre (2012), and Jensen (2016). Those monitoring nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and/or ozone (O₃) in a mobile framework include: Norwegian CITI-Sense-MOB project (Castell, 2015); system tested in Turin, Italy by Velasco (2016); swiss OpenSense and OpenSense 2 projects (e.g. Hasenfratz, Saukh, & Thiele, 2012; Hasenfratz, Saukh, Sturzenegger, & Thiele, 2012; Hundt, 2017; Maag, 2018); Varela (2009) and Lopez-Peña (2010) in Spain; also in Italy, the work by Penza (2017); and the project City Scanner (Anjomshoaa, 2019) in the United States of America.

Several challenges exist to achieve sensible measurements from metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) or from electro-chemical (EC) sensors such as: reproducibility, stability, uncertainty, drift, cross sensitivities. For comparison of sensor performance, sensors tests made in chambers, and field measurements these problems are addressed in various ways, a brief overview is given in Table 1. Jiao (2016) reports on the performance of commercial systems compared to monitoring stations operated a national environmental agency. Namely, several sensors of three commercial

systems were tested. One of them equipped with a MOS sensor and two other with EC sensors. The Pearson correlation coefficient r , for about 8 months of hourly O_3 values from these sensors to the reference values, was reported to be in the range of 0.91–0.97 for MOS type sensors; where as for the EC sensors a large variation was found between the two commercial systems (r : 0.39–0.45 and r : 0.91–0.97). For NO_2 only one EC device reached a reasonably high correlation (0.42–0.76). Linear regression of sensor outputs against the reference instrument, plus other explanatory variables (e.g. ambient temperature and humidity, and number of measurement days) was applied to a selection of the sensors, showing some improvement in the correlation. Similar work by Spindelle (2015) suggested that linear regression yields good results for O_3 , and that for NO_2 supervised learning improves the calibration to the reference instrument. The EuNetAir joint exercise (Borrego, 2016) reported r^2 : 0.12–0.77 for O_3 , and r^2 : 0.02–0.89 for NO_2 . Here, we verify the performance of our sensor box with a side-by-side evaluation against a commercial system equipped with MOS sensors.

The organisation of this paper is as follows: calibration steps of EC sensors and the steps we follow for the comparison to MOS sensor are in the next section; the results of our comparison and calibration as well as a discussion are presented in Results section. In the last section we conclude the paper and give an outlook to our current and future work in last section.

2. Methods and approach

2.1. Description of sensor-box and commercial system

Our sensor-box is aimed at monitoring air quality (i.e. NO_2 , O_3 , CO, PM_{10} , PM_{25} , PM_1 , TVOC, ECO_2), temperature, humidity, pressure and other environmental parameters such as light and noise. It can be mounted on a moving frame, and transmit geo-tagged data via wireless networks. It can be powered via a solar photovoltaic panel or a battery. Figure 1 a) shows some of the main components air quality sensor node as laid out in an earlier prototype which combines off-the-shelve analog electrochemical (EC) gas sensors, digital to analog converters (ADC), battery charge controller, global positioning system (gps) receiver, and other sensors (sound, light, ultrafine particle matter, pressure, temperature, volatile organic compounds). Figure 1 b) illustrates the flow of data from the sensor-box sensors to the geo-spatial visualization application. The sensor-box prototype can send data directly to the internet of things (IoT)

Table 1. Overview of sensor types, methods applied for calibration and focus of selected publications

Sensor type	Methods	Focus
MOS, EC, IRGA, ^a PI ^b	Manufacturer specification, comparison to reference instruments or other sensor	Review of technical specifications and literature, calibration models, sensor network calibration, performance metrics (Alexandre, 2012; Karagulian, 2019; Maag, 2018; Concas, 2020)
MOS, EC, OPC, ^c NDIR, ^d PI	Linear regression, artificial neural networks, self-organizing maps	Evaluation of low-cost sensors, comparison to reference methods (Lin, 2015; Spinelle, 2015; Borrego, 2016; Castell, 2017; Jiao, 2016)
EC, MOS, NDIR, PI	Filtering, curve fitting, regression, domain knowledge, support vector machine, regression and classification	Field measurements, chamber tests, identification of sources (Thorson, 2019; Esatbeyoglu, 2020; Hasenfratz, Saukh, & Thiele, 2012; Mead, 2013; Brienza, 2015; Kim, 2018)
^a Infrared Gas Absorption Spectra; ^b Photo Ionization; ^c Optical Particle Counters; ^d Nondispersive Infrared Note: Castell (2017) reports in detailed about the calibration of EC sensors from the same manufacturer as in this study stating measurement repeatability in pbb as 7.9 and 5.4 for NO_2 and O_3 respectively; Maag (2018) reviews in detail different calibration approaches; Karagulian (2019) offers a detailed summary of correlation coefficients achieved with various methods; Concas (2020) focuses on <i>re-calibration</i> with machine learning approaches.		

cloud. Alternatively, it can send it via our gateway or using the infrastructure of a low power wide area network (LPWAN), particularly those gateways operating with the LoRaWAN open standard. As our application considers the sensors to be mounted on vehicles, a gateway fixed at a location common to their routes can be reached via WiFi allowing for large quantities of data to be transfer at high speed, as well as the boxes to receive software or configuration updates. Moreover, it has a recording mode that allows it to save high frequency measurements in memory which can be transferred to the gateway or accessed via the memory card.

As illustrated in Figure 1 a), the EC sensors in the sensor-box are mounted on a circuit board that includes an analogue potentiostat circuit (AFE) provided by the same manufacturer. The sensor cells (composed of electrodes, electrolyte, and filters) generate a current when they come in contact with the sample gas, which is in turned transformed to a voltage by the analog circuit. The voltage output is (except for the interferences with other gases, and distortion from temperature and humidity) linear to the gas concentration. Typically, the measured signal is given by the difference between the working (WE) and the auxiliary electrode (AE), this is further explained in the next section.

In order to verify the performance of our sensor-box, a commercial system that can monitor similar air quality and environmental parameters, albeit with different type of gas sensors, is used for comparison and calibration. The MOS sensors in the commercial systems are recommended by the manufacturer for use in monitoring automobile exhausts gases (NO₂), and for gas leak detection and outdoor air quality (O₃). The commercial system itself is aimed at the consumer market for indicative indoor air quality, here, we treat it as a black box to exercise the calibration of our sensors. According to Spindelle (2015), electrochemical (EC) and metal-oxide semiconductor (MOS) are considered to have shortest response time, high sensitivity and good repeatability compared to other low-cost sensor types. Table 2 describes some of the main specifications of MOS and EC sensors for NO₂ and O₃, note that these are in principle suitable for indicative monitoring at the parts per billion (ppb) scale.

2.2. Corrections and calibration of electrochemical sensors

In principle, two corrections are of importance to get sensible output from EC amperometric sensors: (1) initial offset corrections, and (2) temperature correction of the background current. Part of the initial offset corrections applied to the raw outputs (WE_u, WA_u) of our sensor module (AFE with NO₂-A43F and OX-A431 sensors, ADC) are so-called *electronic* offsets (WE_e, AE_e) which intend to compensate any offsets introduced by the circuit board. The other part corresponds to offsets of the sensor cell itself (WE₀, AE₀) when measuring *clean* air (i.e. *zero air* with very low content of hydrocarbon impurities, at 101 kPa, 23 ± 2 °C, 40 ± 15 %RH). Typically, offsets from the electronics are much larger than those from the sensor cells, in our experience WE_e, AE_e, WE₀, and AE₀ are in the order of 335.5 ± 55.7, 336.1 ± 55.0, -4.9 ± 4.0, and -2.2 ± 1.6 mV. Under controlled laboratory conditions with *zero air*, these initial offset

Figure 1 a) Main components of air quality sensor node: gas sensors (NO₂-A43F, OX-A31), battery charge controller, and analog to digital converter

Figure 1 b) Connectivity concept of sensor-box, in blue the components outside the IoT that we control, the LPWAN is an open LoRaWAN

corrections should yield a stable positive voltage output and therefore the gas concentration c should be positive around zero. Equation 1 shows the conversion from a corrected sensor output (WE_{cor} , WA_{cor}) in mV to gas concentration c in ppb

$$c = \frac{WE_{cor} - AE_{cor}}{S} \quad (1)$$

where $WE_{cor} = WE_u - \text{offset}$ and $AE_{cor} = AE_u - \text{offset}$; WE_u and AE_u are the raw digitized values before any corrections; offset could be the total initial offsets (i.e., $WE_e + WE_0$ or $AE_e + AE_0$, respectively) or simply the electronic ones, as indicated in ANN 803-05, 2019; S is the sensor module sensitivity in mV/ppb (Table 2 shows the range of these parameters in our sensor fleet).

The other type of correction is related to the ambient temperature directly on top of the sensor cell, because it is known that it affects the current generated by the cell. The manufacturer provides guidance (ANN 803-05, 2019) on how to apply four possible algorithms and the corresponding temperature parametrizations of the additional correction factors. The first three of the algorithms are very similar to Equation 1, except that the quantity subtracted to the working electrode signal (WE_{cor}) is corrected to compensate for temperature. The fourth suggested option for correction, completely neglects the signal from the auxiliary electrode, and simply uses the initial offset corrections of the working electrode and a temperature compensation factor. Equation 2 shows the corresponding equations, from top to bottom algorithms 1, 2, 3, and 4. The compensation parameters n_T , k_T , k'_T , and k''_T are also given in ANN 803-5, (2019) for various sensor types as a function of temperature T .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(a1)} \quad c &= \frac{WE_{cor} - n_T AE_{cor}}{S} \\ \text{(a2)} \quad c &= \frac{WE_{cor} - k_T \left(\frac{WE_0}{AE_0} \right) AE_{cor}}{S} \\ \text{(a3)} \quad c &= \frac{WE_{cor} - ((WE_0 - AE_0) + k'_T AE_{cor})}{S} \\ \text{(a4)} \quad c &= \frac{WE_{cor} - (WE_0 + k''_T)}{S} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The formulas above are not guaranteed to deliver a perfect output compared to other sensors or reference instruments, as discussed by Mead (2013), Popoola (2016), Cross (2017), and in the manufacturer technical note ANN 803-05 (2019). Thus, statistical or empirical corrections are commonly applied in order to re-calibrate the sensor signals to a reference instrument, to a pool of data from several other sensors, or to account for specific operating conditions of the sensors. For this verification, we take three steps: estimate concentration measured by EC sensor with different corrections; select a correction that maintains or improves the correlation to the reference; and apply a linear correction to calibrate the measured concentration to the reference.

The NO_2 concentration is estimated with Equation 2, and also by converting the EC sensor outputs to a gas concentration only with Equation 1 in three ways: without any offset (offset=0); taking only the electronic offset (offset={ WE_e, AE_e }); and taking the electronic plus the sensor zero offset (offset={ $WE_e + WE_0, AE_e + AE_0$ }). These correspond to raw, diffE, and diffT in the Results and discussion section. In order to compare the corrections and select one for the calibration, we calculate the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between each correction and the reference measurements from the MOS sensor. Bootstrapping these estimations of r let us get a sense of confidence with the standard error of r for each correction case. The parameters (m , b) of the linear correction $y_{cal} = (y - b)/m$ are calculated by minimizing the sum of squared errors between the measured EC and MOS NO_2 concentrations. Thus, the common closed form solution to the linear least-squares problem is applied to the linear model $\hat{y} = mx + b$ to minimize $\sum((y - \hat{y})^2 / \sigma_y^2)$, where y and x are the EC and MOS gas concentrations respectively. The formal limitations of this approach are the necessary assumptions that x are true values (e.g. without uncertainties) and that the uncertainty of y is a known Gaussian distribution. Implementation of these calculations is done with open source libraries, namely the linear algebra packages supported by NumPy and other libraries part of the SciPy stack (Virtanen, 2020).

2.3. Measurement set up for verification

Sensor nodes have been placed side-by-side in various settings, including indoors in a suburban environment, outdoors in an urban park, in office space, and in a moving framework in an urban area. Here, we report on the indoor suburban setting measurement campaign, where two of our sensors nodes were placed next to two commercial

Table 2. Technical specifications of EC sensors (OX-A431, NO2-A43F) in sensor-box and MOS sensors (MiCS-4514 for NO₂, and MiCS-2614 for O₃) in commercial system as stated in manufacturers data sheets

Sensor	Specifications
OX-A431 [§]	Range ^a up to 20 ppm. Sensor cell sensitivity: -200 to -650 nA/ppm at 1ppm O ₃ (from data sheet); -0.467 ± 0.269 nA/ppb, NO ₂ cross sensitivity -0.538 ± 0.149 nA/ppb. Sensor module ^b sensitivity: 0.389 ± 0.039 mV/ppb, NO ₂ cross sensitivity 0.392 ± 0.109 mV/ppb.
NO2-A43F [#]	Range ^c up to 20 ppm. Sensor cell sensitivity: -175 to -450 nA/ppm at 2ppm NO ₂ (from data sheet), -0.356 ± 0.057 nA/ppb (average and standard deviation from manufacturer calibration sheets of our sensors). Sensor module sensitivity: 0.260 ± 0.042 mV/ppb.
MiCS-4514 [*]	Range 0.05 to 10 ppm.
MiCS-2614 ⁺	Range ^d 10 to 1000 ppb.

[§]OX-A431 Oxidising Gas Sensor Ozone + Nitrogen Dioxide 4-Electrode, available online at <http://www.alphasense.com/WEB1213/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/OX-A431.pdf>.
[#]NO2-A43F Nitrogen Dioxide Sensor 4-Electrode, available online at <http://www.alphasense.com/WEB1213/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/OX-A431.pdf>.
^{*}MiCS-4514 Data sheet, 0278 rev 15, available online at https://www.sgxsensortech.com/content/uploads/2014/08/0278_Datasheet-MiCS-4514.pdf.
⁺MiCS-2614 Data sheet 1087 rev 6, available online at https://www.sgxsensortech.com/content/uploads/2014/07/1087_Datasheet-MiCS-2614-rev-6.pdf.
^aAccording to Spinelle (2015) O₃ EC sensors can perform within 25 % uncertainty, however NO₂ EC sensors may have uncertainty larger than 30 %. Sensitivities expressed in nA/ppb or mV/ppb are average and standard deviation from manufacturer calibration sheets of our sensors.
^bThe sensor module comprises sensors OX-A431 and NO2-A43F and an analog front end (AFE) circuit which implements a potentiostat to render the output as a voltage output instead of the current generated by the sensor cell. Refer to Analogue Front End (AFE) Alphasense A4 Air Quality Gas Sensors (2 sensor AFE 810-0021-00), available online at <http://www.alphasense.com/WEB1213/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/AFE.pdf>.
^cJensen (2016) reports the lower bound on the range at around 4 ppb; Mead (2013), and Popoola (2016) reported a lower detection limit as low as 1 ppb NO₂ for EC; also high sensor-to-sensor reproducibility (R² values of 0.9532, 0.8361 and 0.9363 for CO, NO and NO₂ respectively).
^dLösch (2008) performed a detailed characterization at constant temperature of a similar MOS sensor for O₃ reporting accurate sensor response to O₃ from 0 to 100 ppb. Hasenfratz, Saukh, Sturzenegger, and Thiele (2012) report an average error, after calibration, of 2.74 ± 4.19 ppb from an O₃ MOS sensor compared to high-quality measurement instruments. Similarly, Hasenfratz, Saukh, and Thiele (2012) report down to +/-2 ppb error, an order of magnitude less than the technical specifications of the MOS sensors used in their studies.

Note the following manufacturers disclaimers: specifications reflect the performance of standalone sensors; specific devices using these sensors may claim different specifications since sensor characteristics may differ when installed in different instruments; specifications provided are for brand new sensors, performance may change over time.

systems. We focus on a one-to-one comparison, noting that the observed inter-sensor variability will be addressed in future work. The campaign took place end of January-February 2020, indoors in a suburban area, close to our university campus. The devices were located next to each other, and the use of the office space was kept under normal conditions. Sensors have been powered for several hours prior to this experiment as part of the sensor-box prototyping, during the experiment the sensor-box was always connected to the power supply, thus the sensor module it-self is powered through the on-board battery. The commercial device was always connected to the power supply and to the

local internet connection. The sensor-box was run in recording mode and data access via the memory card; the commercial system via its cloud application interface.

3. Results and discussion

Data collected during almost nine days, from January 29 23:16:00 until 2020-02-07 22:59:00, is presented here to verify the performance of our sensor-box. After removing null values, but without any filtering nor removing of potential outliers, we proceed to estimate NO_2 concentration in a data set containing ~ 150 hours of raw output from our EC and temperature sensors and the corresponding signals from the commercial system. Raw values in mV are converted to gas concentration in ppb with semi-empirical formulas suggested by the manufacturer (Equation 2; a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , and a_4 in Figure 2). Next, we compare these methods at different time resolutions in terms of their correlation to the commercial system. As the signals are re-sampled to longer sampling time, naturally, there is a slight increase in r . However, since the data set is not so large, these estimations show much larger standard error relative to shorter sampling times. Overall, we reach moderate to strong correlation r : 0.46–0.64, comparable to the other works. Important to notice is that around the minute-resolution, we can confidently reach higher correlation, $r = 0.58 \pm 0.01$, without temperature correction. This owes partly to the stable conditions of our test, however, the observed response of the working electrode and the auxiliary electrode versus temperature was very similar (not shown here) even in ranges where the correction factors have an influence on the calculated concentration. Thus, supporting this analysis of correlation, which shows that in this case the temperature correction tends to distort rather than substantially improve the sensor output correlation to the reference measurements. Particularly, this is true for algorithm 1 at shorter sampling times as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Bootstrapped Pearson correlation coefficient r between the sensor-box (a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , a_4 , diffE , diffT , and raw) and the commercial system. In each group of bars signals are re-sampled as indicated, from 10 seconds to 6 hours; each bars corresponds to different correction algorithms applied to the sensor-box measurements, as indicated in the color legend from algorithm 1 (dark blue) to raw values from the electrodes without corrections (light yellow). Black lines represent the standard deviation of r . Original sampling time of sensor-box is ~ 10 seconds and the commercial system data can be queried at maximum 1-minute resolution.

For the last step of the verification, we take the corrected EC concentrations and calibrate them to the MOS sensor. The focus is on calibrating the 5-minute resolution signal, potentially any of the corrections could give lower error between to the reference MOS, except for algorithm 1. A linear fit yields the correction parameters, as described in section 2.2. From data reported in the NO-A43F sensor data sheet, that shows its response to step changes of known NO_2 concentration, we estimated the uncertainty of NO_2 concentrations to be less than 1 ppb. However, in the same data sheet it is stated that the AFE reduces noise down to 15 ppb. We take the larger value, as the uncertainty in the field is expected to be larger than in laboratory conditions reported. The results of the calibrations for the different correction methods are shown in Figures 3. A calibration tends to one in the x-axis as the sum of squared errors between the reference measurement x and the calibrated measurement y_{cal} tends to zero; it tends to one in the y-axis as the NRMSE tends to zero. Thus, better results of a calibration would be at the right-top of the plot. We reach low NRMSE values, but the better calibrations can only *explain* about half of the variance of the reference measurement. As expected from the correlation analyses, the combination of the two metrics in Figure 3 indicates that temperature corrections are marginal for this case, particularly, that of algorithm 1 yields higher error. A snippet of a time series

of calibrated concentration and reference concentration are shown in Figure 4, showing that generally there is a good agreement between our sensor-box and the commercial system once the calibration is performed.

Figure 3 Comparison of linear calibrations based on different correction methods, legend shows the corresponding correction algorithm, the metric of x-axis of the plot, and the normalized root-mean-squared error (NRMSE) between the reference x and the calibrated signal y_{cal} . RMSE is normalized to the range of the NO_2 concentrations measured by the reference commercial system (~ 150 ppb).

Figure 4 Histogram and hourly values of sensor-box calibrated output and commercial system for a segment of the data set.

4. Conclusions and outlook

Our low-cost sensor-box for air quality, noise, and light features various connectivity options and it provides geo-tagged data from its surrounding environment. An IoT cloud platform supports the post-processing and applications for data visualization. A complete data flow pipeline from sensors to visualization has been implemented and tested. Here, we described our steps for the verification of the NO_2 sensor output, showing that it performs well compared to a commercial system. Next steps in our development include verification of O_3 and particle matter (PM) in a similar fashion as presented here, and validation against reference instruments. Extensive geo-tagged data gathering campaigns will be essential to verify the performance on the field and evaluate in depth (i) inter-sensor variability, (ii) influence of environmental conditions (temperature, humidity, and presence of other compounds), (iii) data quality and long-term performance (in terms of sensors and data pipeline).

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References

1. Künzli N, Perez L, Rapp R. Air quality and health. European Respiratory Society; 2010.
2. Switzerland country briefing - The European environment - state and outlook 2015 [Internet]. European Environment Agency. 2020 [cited 2020Sep8]. Available from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/soer/2015/countries/switzerland>
3. Morawska L, Thai PK, Liu X, Asumadu-Sakyi A, Ayoko G, Bartonova A, Bedini A, Chai F, Christensen B, Dunbabin M, Gao J. Applications of low-cost sensing technologies for air quality monitoring and exposure assessment: How far have they gone?. *Environment international*. 2018 Jul 1;116:286-99.
4. Karagulian F, Barbiere M, Kotsev A, Spinelle L, Gerboles M, Lagler F, Redon N, Crunaire S, Borowiak A. Review of the performance of low-cost sensors for air quality monitoring. *Atmosphere*. 2019 Sep;10(9):506.
5. Penza M. Low-cost sensors for outdoor air quality monitoring. In *Advanced Nanomaterials for Inexpensive Gas Microsensors 2020* Jan 1 (pp. 235-288). Elsevier.
6. Aleixandre M, Gerboles M. Review of small commercial sensors for indicative monitoring of ambient gas. *Chem. Eng. Trans.* 2012;30.
7. Jensen CK. Assessing the applicability of low-cost electrochemical gas sensors for urban air quality monitoring. *DTU Environment*. 2016 Jan.
8. Castell N, Kobernus M, Liu HY, Schneider P, Lahoz W, Berre AJ, Noll J. Mobile technologies and services for environmental monitoring: The Citi-Sense-MOB approach. *Urban climate*. 2015 Dec 1;14:370-82.
9. Velasco A, Ferrero R, Gandino F, Montrucchio B, Rebaudengo M. A mobile and low-cost system for environmental monitoring: A case study. *Sensors*. 2016 May;16(5):710.
10. Hasenfratz D, Saukh O, Thiele L. On-the-fly calibration of low-cost gas sensors. In *European Conference on Wireless Sensor Networks 2012* Feb 15 (pp. 228-244). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
11. Hasenfratz D, Saukh O, Sturzenegger S, Thiele L. Participatory air pollution monitoring using smartphones. *Mobile Sensing*. 2012 Apr 16;1:1-5.
12. Hundt PM, Müller M, Mangold M, Tuzson B, Scheidegger P, Looser H, Hüglin C, Emmenegger L. Spectroscopic real-time monitoring of NO₂ for city scale modelling. *prep. Atm. Meas. Techn.* 2017.
13. Maag B, Zhou Z, Thiele L. A survey on sensor calibration in air pollution monitoring deployments. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*. 2018 Jul 6;5(6):4857-70.
14. Varela G, Paz-Lopez A, Duro RJ, Lopez-Pena F, Gonzalez-Castano FJ. An integrated system for urban pollution monitoring through a public transportation based opportunistic mobile sensor network. In *2009 IEEE International Workshop on Intelligent Data Acquisition and Advanced Computing Systems: Technology and Applications 2009* Sep 21 (pp. 148-153). IEEE.
15. Lopez-Peña F, Varela G, Paz-Lopez A, Duro RJ, González-Castaño FJ. Public transportation based dynamic urban pollution monitoring system. *Sensors & Transducers*. 2010 Feb 1;8:13.
16. Penza M, Suriano D, Pfister V, Prato M, Cassano G. Urban air quality monitoring with networked low-cost sensor-systems. In *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute Proceedings 2017* (Vol. 1, No. 4, p. 573).
17. Anjomshoa A, Duarte F, Rennings D, Matarazzo TJ, deSouza P, Ratti C. City scanner: Building and scheduling a mobile sensing platform for smart city services. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*. 2018 May 21;5(6):4567-79.
18. Jiao W, Hagler G, Williams R, Sharpe R, Brown R, Garver D, Judge R, Caudill M, Rickard J, Davis M, Weinstock L. Community Air Sensor Network (CAIRSENSE) project: evaluation of low-cost sensor performance in a suburban environment in the southeastern United States. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*. 2016 Nov 1;9(11).
19. Spinelle L, Gerboles M, Villani MG, Aleixandre M, Bonavitacola F. Field calibration of a cluster of low-cost available sensors for air quality monitoring. Part A: Ozone and nitrogen dioxide. *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*. 2015 Aug 1;215:249-57.
20. Borrego C, Costa AM, Ginja J, Amorim M, Coutinho M, Karatzas K, Sioumis T, Katsifarakis N, Konstantinidis K, De Vito S, Esposito E. Assessment of air quality microsensors versus reference methods: The EuNetAir joint exercise. *Atmospheric Environment*. 2016 Dec 1;147:246-63.
21. Castell N, Dauge FR, Schneider P, Vogt M, Lerner U, Fishbain B, Broday D, Bartonova A. Can commercial low-cost sensor platforms contribute to air quality monitoring and exposure estimates?. *Environment international*. 2017 Feb 1;99:293-302.
22. Concas F, Mineraud J, Lagerspetz E, Varjonen S, Puolamäki K, Nurmi P, Tarkoma S. Low-cost outdoor air quality monitoring and in-field sensor calibration. 2020 Feb 5; arXiv:submit/3032485; [eess.SP].
23. Lin C, Gillespie J, Schuder MD, Duberstein W, Beverland IJ, Heal MR. Evaluation and calibration of Aeroqual series 500 portable gas sensors for accurate measurement of ambient ozone and nitrogen dioxide. *Atmospheric Environment*. 2015 Jan 1;100:111-6.
24. Thorson J, Collier-Oxandale A, Hannigan M. Using A Low-Cost Sensor Array and Machine Learning Techniques to Detect Complex Pollutant Mixtures and Identify Likely Sources. *Sensors*. 2019 Jan;19(17):3723.
25. Esatbeyoglu E, Cassebaum O, Arras F, Saake G. Data Driven Concept for Sensor Data Adaptation of Electrochemical Sensors for Mobile Air Quality Measurements. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*. 2020 Feb 21;167(4):047518.

26. Mead MI, Popoola OA, Stewart GB, Landshoff P, Calleja M, Hayes M, Baldovi JJ, McLeod MW, Hodgson TF, Dicks J, Lewis A. The use of electrochemical sensors for monitoring urban air quality in low-cost, high-density networks. *Atmospheric Environment*. 2013 May 1;70:186-203.
27. Brienza S, Galli A, Anastasi G, Bruschi P. A low-cost sensing system for cooperative air quality monitoring in urban areas. *Sensors*. 2015 Jun;15(6):12242-59.
28. Kim J, Shusterman AA, Lieschke KJ, Newman C, Cohen RC. The Berkeley atmospheric CO₂ observation network: Field calibration and evaluation of low-cost air quality sensors. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*. 2018 Apr 6;11(4):1937-46.
29. Alphasense Ltd. Correcting for background currents in four electrode toxic gas sensors: Alphasense Application Note, ANN 803-5. 2019 Jun. Available upon request.
30. Popoola OA, Stewart GB, Mead MI, Jones RL. Development of a baseline-temperature correction methodology for electrochemical sensors and its implications for long-term stability. *Atmospheric Environment*. 2016 Dec 1;147:330-43.
31. Cross ES, Williams LR, Lewis DK, Magoon GR, Onasch TB, Kaminsky ML, Worsnop DR, Jayne JT. Use of electrochemical sensors for measurement of air pollution: correcting interference response and validating measurements. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*. 2017 Sep 1;10(9):3575.
32. Virtanen P, Gommers R, Oliphant TE, Haberland M, Reddy T, Cournapeau D, Burovski E, Peterson P, Weckesser W, Bright J, van der Walt SJ. SciPy 1.0: fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in Python. *Nature methods*. 2020 Mar;17(3):261-72.